

ORGANIZING AN EFFECTIVE TEACHING METHOD FOR PRESCHOOL EDUCATION

Makhamadaliyeva Oynisa Kamoliddin qizi

Chirchik State Pedagogical University

Email: moynisa@mail.ru

ABSTRACT

This article talks about the interactive development methods, the content of interactive education, the organization of modern technologies for preschool children in an entertaining and new system.

Keywords: *integration of teaching of preschool education subjects, methods and tools, traditional method, interactive methods, innovative forms.*

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada interfaol ishlab chiqaruvchi metodlar, interaktiv ta'limning mazmuni maktabgacha bo'lgan bolalar uchun zamonaviy texnologiyalarni ko'ngilochar va yangicha tizimda tashkil etish haqida so'z yuritiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: *maktabgacha ta'lim fanlarini o'qitishni integrasiyalash, metod va ishlab chiqarish, an'anaviy metod, interfaol metodlar, innovatsion shakllar.*

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье рассказывается об интерактивных методах развития, содержании интерактивного обучения, организации современных технологий для детей дошкольного возраста в развлекательной и новой системе.

Ключевые слова: *интеграция обучения предметам дошкольного образования, методы и средства, традиционный метод, интерактивные методы, инновационные формы.*

INTRODUCTION

Currently, there is an interest in increasing the effectiveness of education using interactive methods (innovative pedagogical and information technologies) in the educational process. Attention is increasing day by day. Modern technologies are used for training students aimed at finding the acquired knowledge by themselves, studying and analyzing it independently, and even drawing their own conclusions. In this process, the teacher creates conditions for the development, formation, learning and education of individuals and the team, and at the same time, he performs the functions of management and guidance. In such an educational process, the student becomes the main figure.

A rapid search for developing technologies that predict the effective use of all analyzed methods in solving theoretical or practical tasks in preschool educational institutions of the Republic of Uzbekistan and improvement-reproduction of existing traditional technologies are being carried out. Developing technologies in pre-school education are understood as the theory of implementation of theoretically based methods and tools of the education and training system, which make it possible to increase educational goals into useful practice. In the effective use of developing technologies in pre-school education, educational goals are given the same, and their sequence is aimed at the same type of educational organization as the main goal of maintaining the final evaluation criterion of the results achieved. Pedagogical technologies developing in preschool education are directed to the educational system, as well as the psychological development process of the child, their social characteristics, creative abilities, spiritual development.

Technologies that develop the field of education in the environment of humanization are creative management of the child from the psychological side, or rather, managing them as they are; orientation to the positive-personal world; identifying and revealing the qualities bestowed on the child by the universe; current training in the future improvement system; educate freely; supporting needs from the social side; an important leading process of the age of preschoolers is the use of game

activities; Due to the fact that the implementation of educational and training activities is forced to carry out all the time assessment, results and analysis of this system, it is necessary to build various developing technologies from the diagnostic side. The quality of education is directly related to the student's achievement of the result. It is necessary to look at the development of the developing pedagogical technology as an important gift to the student, to trust the child, to recognize him as a high expert, to provide for the needs of the child with all the laws and rights strengthening treatment.

Studying the many areas of law of controlling and correcting the quality of preschool education, i.e. the control and correction of the learning process that has the power to achieve the quality of education or learning capacity that is reinforced from above. must be controlled with Our country's educational technology, teaching capacity is constantly changing, and the federal country established by authorized access is refusing to live a life that is inextricably linked to the educational criteria. Problems arise and reduce the amount of time for a fundamental review of individual equipment in an important educational system, and all these events are connected with the new law, the production and implementation of social educational technologies, teaching methods and o It requires research on educational systems and teaching methods and forms. It is necessary to understand the main qualities of those who are able to consciously freely choose developing technologies by quality hands and knowledge, and also those who achieve favorable results in education and upbringing.

Extensive use of developing interactive and interactive technologies has been introduced within the framework of a qualitatively developed educational system. Currently, social communication technologies, i.e., information and communication technologies are rapidly improving, the importance and necessary conditions for the formation of all types of pre-school educational system are being created. These, in turn, are reflected in new educational processes. These are the standard requirements for the use of interactive learning and interactive technologies in preschool education. Application of modern computer technologies for preschool students in a new, useful and comprehensive system helps to improve the quality of conscious speech, solve the

shortcomings of ecological, aesthetic, mathematical improvement, as well as creativity, imagination, memory system skills, logical speech helps to improve. On the other hand, the widespread use of interactive learning systems makes it possible for every participant in the field of education to control or, if not, every point of view.

CONCLUSION

The improvement of the comprehensively developed modern population requires the integration of the experience of development messages, pedagogical research and the organization of educational activities by radically changing them, and one of the areas of solving these shortcomings is an important approach to strengthening educational activities with students.

REFERENCES

1. Tolipov O', Usmanboeva M. Practical foundations of pedagogical technologies in preschool education. T.: "Science". 2006.
2. Istanko I.V. Children of senior preschool age // Activities in the management of preschool education educational institution, 2004.
3. Patanko I.V. Project activity with preschool children. "Preschool educational institution" magazine #4. 2004.
4. Madumarov T., Kamoliddinov M. Fundamentals of innovative pedagogical technology and its application in the educational process. T.: "Talqin", 2012.